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Teaching Students a Foreign Language as a Form of Organization of Their Knowledge

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Abstract

At present, the global goal of mastering a foreign language is the ability and skill to participate in the dialogue of cultures. At the same time, it is not just about knowing the language but about the ability to use it in real communication, that is, about practical knowledge of the language. Therefore, it is necessary to have educational standards that would imply an increase in the effectiveness of the educational process in which various methods, techniques and organizational forms of education would contribute to the complete organization of the knowledge of the students. In view of this, the following aspects are considered in the article: peculiarities of teaching university students a foreign language; the organization of teaching a foreign language in a functional context; the basic principles of teaching a foreign language; basic methodological approaches for teaching students in the context of the form of organization of their knowledge; increase of intellectual and general cultural level of students' knowledge when studying a foreign language; opportunities to improve the form of organization of knowledge when teaching students.

Keywords: language education; cognitive capacities; construction of knowledge; foreign language; methodological approaches.

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Introduction

Knowledge of a foreign language becomes today a mandatory component of the professional training of a modern specialist in any sphere. That is why a foreign language in a university is not only professionally-oriented but cultural, linguistic and intellectual as a whole. At the same time, the tasks of teaching students a foreign language include the cognitive needs of young people, and this, by definition, actualizes the problem of structuring the organization of their knowledge. And the use of a foreign language in future professional activity, in the long run, will always be directed to the process of self-education in this or that area (Khuziakhmetov & Valeev, 2017). In this regard, a foreign language as one of the means of exploring the world occupies a special place in the system of modern education due to its social, cognitive and developmental functions. On this basis, teaching a foreign language has its own specifics, which, in particular, is related to the intensification of the learning process through the cognitive activity of students, and therefore through the competent organization of their knowledge. Therefore, it is necessary to create conditions for a maximum realization of the intellectual potential of students taking into account such important features of students as the level of self-knowledge as a prerequisite for personality development; readiness for self-assertion; the need for occupation; the desire to test own strengths and character; the desire for self-determination from the point of view of searching for one's own moral ideal; defining own values, etc. (Valeev & Muzafarova, 2016). In order to do this, the following provisions are taken into account in the university when organizing students' learning process: the need to achieve results of their activities (for example, it comes from general tasks of mastering a foreign language); presence of incentive elements; ensuring the complexity of activities when the study of a foreign language is considered as a set of elements that makes up a single whole; implementation of educational work in each specific case is ensured by the correspondence of the organization of the educational process to its content at the level of the modern science.

In this regard, the organization of knowledge in the course of studying a foreign language is carried out within the framework of teaching students productive social interaction in a foreign environment. This implies the development of logical, critical and creative thinking; mandatory availability of independent work focused on the application of acquired knowledge, skills, and experience in practice. Thus, in order to achieve the goal of teaching students a foreign language in the context of organizing their knowledge the educational process in the university should be organized in such a way that it is as efficient and optimal as possible. This poses the following tasks for the teacher: determining the logic of carrying out each practical lesson, taking into account all its stages; determining what tasks and exercises to offer students for the development of skills in different types of cognitive activity; determining formulations and instructions for assignments and exercises that are communicative in nature; determining formats and genres that future professionals will use in their professional activities; determining the optimal forms of work, methods and techniques for students to use in the process of their independent work (Nazarova & Valeev, 2017). The main thing is that, on the basis of the problems under consideration, the form of the organization of knowledge should be closely linked with the study of a foreign language aimed at filling professional knowledge and corresponding language competencies.

Purpose and objectives of the study

The hypothesis of the research is based on the fact that teaching university students a foreign language as a form of organization of their knowledge will be more effective if (1) the organization of teaching university students a foreign language is carried out in a functional context; (2) the ways for

improving the form of organization of knowledge in teaching students are identified; (3) the possibilities for increasing the intellectual and general cultural level of students' knowledge when studying foreign languages are structured; (4) the main methodological approaches in teaching students in the context of the form of organization of their knowledge are used; (5) conditions for the introduction of the fundamental principles of teaching a foreign language are created.

In this study, the following tasks were set (1) to analyze peculiarities of teaching university students a foreign language; (2) to reveal the basic principles of teaching a foreign language; (3) to structure the possibilities for increasing the intellectual and general cultural level of knowledge of students when studying foreign languages; (4) to reveal the main methodological approaches for teaching students in the context of the form of organization of their knowledge; (5) to identify ways for improving the form of organization of knowledge when teaching students.

Literature review

Nowadays, the process of teaching a foreign language is seen as a process of interaction between the teacher and students with the aim of imparting on young people knowledge, skills and values (Kondrateva & Valeev, 2015). In this regard, in the system of knowledge organization of university students when teaching a foreign language can be divided into the following sections: the didactic (or educational) section, the cultural section, and the organizational section. Thus, the didactic section includes a clear set of the educational tasks of each specific lesson as a whole and its constituent elements, as well as its place in the general system of the training course. Then, the optimal content of studied subjects is determined in accordance with the requirements of the curriculum in the foreign language, taking into account the level of students' preparation, including forecasting the level of mastering of scientific and linguistic knowledge and the formation of speech skills. Then, the choice of the most rational methods, and means of teaching, stimulation and control of their optimal interaction at each stage of the exercise is made taking into account a combination of various forms of teamwork with an independent activity of students, and etc.

As for the cultural section, it presupposes deepening of students' ideas about the foreign country's culture through language and broadening of the general outlook. At the same time, the study of a foreign language as a form of organization of knowledge gives students the opportunity to master means of perception and expression of thoughts about objects, phenomena, their connections and relations through a new language, which acts in two forms: oral and written. And when these forms of communication are mastered, the communicative goal of teaching the subject 'Foreign Language' is reached which implies mastering of sociocultural knowledge and skills. And this means that cultural orientation of education ensures the realization of not only general educational but also practical goals.

Further, the organizational section is focused on the formation and development of students' cognitive interests, positive motivation for educational and cognitive activities, skills and acquired habits of independent mastering of linguistic knowledge, as well as ensuring a close connection between learning and life. At the same time, the organization of knowledge when teaching a foreign language can be either direct (group or individual form of work with students) and indirect (for example, distance learning) organizational forms of training that reflect the nature of communication between its participants.

Provided a clear organization of knowledge, students should acquire the following abilities at the end of the foreign language course: understanding oral (monologue and dialogue) speech in professional topics; knowledge about basic grammar and grammatical constructions; knowledge of the main

terminology in the area; basic writing skills that involve conducting business correspondence and ability to work with various types of documentation (for example, agreements, office notes, summaries, etc.); knowledge of the basics of public speech (for example, preparation of reports, presentations, projects, negotiations, etc.); understanding of a foreign speech while listening to it without distorting the original meaning. In this regard, the basis for structuring the knowledge organization is to use the principle of the modular approach, which involves distribution of educational material into the following modules: a social communication module (social and everyday communication, socio-cultural communication, social and political communication); the module of professional communication (general professional communication, industrial communication) and a control module. It is important to emphasize that it is within the framework of the professional communication module that students, on the one hand, learn English, and, on the other hand, acquire knowledge and develop skills in organizing their cognitive activities by means of a foreign language.

The problem of teaching students a foreign language as a form of organizing their knowledge lies in the contradiction between the demand for teaching English in a university and the inadequacy of using the most effective forms and methods of cognitive activity at all levels of university education. Especially if we take into account the fact that in today's society integration processes are increasingly embracing such serious social spheres as science and education. If a few years ago the main aspect of teaching a foreign language was the ability to read and understand a foreign text, now it acquires a professionally-oriented communicative character. Hence, considering teaching students a foreign language as a form of knowledge organization, it can be assumed that the purpose of the academic subject 'Foreign Language', associated with the development of the future specialist's language competencies, is also in mastering a set of knowledge and skills that is the context of knowledge organizations within the framework of enhancing professional, social and intellectual experience (Khusainova & Valeev, 2018). In this regard, teaching a foreign language has its own peculiarities related to a certain specificity, which is determined by the very content of the subject, practical orientation of instruction and the fact that the foreign language is not only a goal but also a means of instruction. This specificity is determined by the basic psychological, pedagogical and methodological requirements for conducting a class in a foreign language. It includes a communicative aspect (topics are played out in such a way that students in the classroom motivate each other to communicate; for example, when studying the topic 'Acquaintance', students have a chance to introduce each other and ask different questions or engage in a discussion); individualization of the learning process (taking into account individual characteristics of students in all its forms and methods regardless of the features and to what extent they are taken into account; at the same time individualization helps to gradually develop the skills of students which allows us to control and correct the process of their development as a linguistic personality if need be); tasks with speech orientation (associated with the development of the main types of speech activity: speaking, listening, reading and writing); situational training (aimed at developing students' imagination, independent creative activity, as well as motivating to learn a foreign language).

Therefore, the peculiarities of teaching university students a foreign language are, first of all, connected with the communicative aspect of teaching. The main thing is that each session has new topics for discussion, new types of exercises. This is done so that students are diversified and at the same time they do not become bored with learning a foreign language. The great help is the possibility of individualization, connected with the formation of students' individual style of cognitive activity, which, as shown in practice, helps an individual to successfully organize the learning process.

To date, in psychology and the pedagogical science the data necessary for solving the problem under study have been accumulated. The analysis of scientific works has shown that teaching university students a foreign language as a form of organization of their knowledge is investigated at all major levels of its functioning, i.e. theoretical, methodological and practical. Intellectual processes of university students were analyzed by Ivanov (2013), Elukhina (2002), Grachev (2007). Formation of intellectual potential of the individual in the teaching and educational process were considered in the works by Shatilo (1998), Babayants (2005), Pligin (2008). Various aspects of the intellectual-pedagogical concept were studied by scientists Goncharuk (2004), Ishkov (2004), Polat (2000). Technologies for the development of mental capabilities are found in the works by Liver (2002), Bakhtina (2007), Konysheva (1988). Theory and practice of the formation of a professional communicative competence of a specialist speaking a foreign language was studied by scientists Iskandarova (2000), Golikova (2005), Boldyreva (1987). Motivation of students in the process of a professionally-oriented study of a foreign language was examined by Latypov & Sabirova (2016), Belykh (2007), Stepanova (2003). Formation of foreign professional competence of students in teaching a foreign language was studied in the works of Aitov (2006), Tsetlin (2000), Iskrin (2004). Development of student-centered instruction in teaching a foreign language was led by Bondarevskaya (2000), Kaloshina (2000). Various aspects of integrative learning of a foreign language are proposed by Gardner (1983), Klobukova (1995), Sysoev (2006). The problems of the development of cognitive strategies in English classes were studied by Leontiev (1995), Reid (2015), Zhang (2017). The problem we are exploring involves studying educational resources for organizing teaching students a foreign language in order to create opportunities for structuring their knowledge as part of the formation of a future competitive specialist.

Methodology

The methodological basis of the research is an understanding of the learning process and the dialectical method of cognition. In connection with this, the following methods were used in the study: content analysis (comparison of information and didactic content of curricula, textbooks and teaching resources); method of oral and written interview; pedagogical observation; self-analysis and self-evaluation by students of their intellectual and general cultural level of knowledge; surveys; generalization of pedagogical experience; analysis of the research results.

Today the role of the teacher in the pedagogical process changes significantly, which due to the development of innovative technologies, changes its monopoly as the only source of knowledge. Nevertheless, the organization of foreign language training for university students in a functional context presupposes that teachers exercise certain functions that, in one way or another, contribute to the process of organizing students' knowledge. These functions include: a management function (allows the teacher not only to correct the student's actions, but also to make changes in the structure and content of the educational process and on this basis to adjust his educational program; in this connection, there is an increase in cultural mental activity of a young person); a training function (it is closely related to the control function, when, for example, control tasks contribute to the implementation of learning tasks, which is most clearly manifested in receptive types of speech activity – in reading and listening; in this connection, the teacher contributes to the formation of communicative skills); a developing function (associated with the development of the student's personality traits such as independence, perseverance, purposefulness, critical thinking, self-control, including development of memory, attention, perception, etc., which is very important for organizing knowledge); a feedback function (it is a teacher's control, i.e.

obtaining information about the level of student preparation, which helps the latter act intelligently and systematically in the course of their cognitive activity); an evaluation function (associated with the assessment of the student's cognitive activity, when the teacher makes a judgment about the quality of its progress, the degree of activity of the young person and his motivation to organize their own knowledge); a diagnostic function (allows to determine the level of the student's knowledge of studied language, skills and acquired habits at a particular stage of training; it allows to identify gaps in the student's professional preparedness, as well as to identify the causes of gaps); a stimulating function (associated with the psychological aspect, when the student is stimulated through control to training activities, for example, in preparation for the test or an exam).

Fundamental principles of teaching a foreign language are closely interrelated and form a unified system designed to ensure the achievement of stated goals related to the organization of the individual's knowledge. Based on the stated problems, these principles can be arranged according to the following sections:

1) Didactic principles: the principle of consciousness (it presupposes the existence of the ability to independently choose the form of organization of linguistic knowledge); the principle of strength (it ensures the preservation of language material in the memory of the student and the possibility of its use in various communication situations); the principle of activity (it presupposes the speech activity of the student with the aim of activating cognitive activity); the principle of professional competence (it characterizes the ability to do the professional activity on the basis of knowledge of a foreign language);

2) Psychological principles: the principle of motivation (based on the student's understanding of his own motives for foreign-language activity); the principle of step-by-step formation in the formation of skills of speech-activity (it determines the dynamics of changes in the structure of speech activity in the process of learning a foreign language); the principle of individualization (it includes personal, subjective and individual individualization when the activation of the sphere of desires and interests comes to the fore; readiness for effective methods of working on the language, taking into account one's own innate abilities); the principle of accounting for adaptation processes (it involves the development of the ability to properly plan one's cognitive activities);

3) Linguistic principles: the principle of systematization (it helps to treat language as a systemic formation, consisting of interrelated elements of different levels); the principle of concentricity (it provides for a clear selection and introduction of lexical and grammatical material for the purpose of participating in speech communication already at the early stages of learning a foreign language); the principle of functionality (it helps to construct statements with regard to the form and meaning of grammatical phenomena in their unity);

4) Methodological principles, consisting of the following groups: general methodological principles (communicative orientation of studying a foreign language; taking into account the peculiarities of the native language; maximum use of exercises); private methodological principles (the principle of the intensity of the initial stage of studying a foreign language; the principle of learning a foreign language according to speech patterns; the principle of combining language training with speech practice; the principle of interrelation of all types of speech activity; the principle of situational and thematic knowledge organization); special methodological principles (principles of teaching the phonetic, lexical and grammatical aspects of speech in another language; the principles of teaching reading, listening, writing and written language; principles of training in dialogue).

Modern practice of improving the foreign language preparation of students as a form of organizing their knowledge is at the center of attention of the psychological and pedagogical science where various pedagogical approaches to achieving of this goal are being explored. It seems to us that the most productive methodological approaches for teaching students a foreign language in the context of knowledge organization are the following approaches:

1) humanistic approach (creation of conditions for active and free development of the personality in the activity; the possibility of choosing one's own method of mastering a foreign language; the feeling of being safe from criticism and prosecution for mistakes);

2) person-oriented approach (an independent selection of tasks of various complexity and volume; the variation in the pace of mastering the educational material; the use of individual creative assignments to create a situation of success);

3) practice-oriented approach (the study of a foreign language based on the active professional activity of the individual and their personal interest in acquiring knowledge);

4) integrative approach (a holistic view of one's own cognitive activity 'from one's own point of view' on the basis of qualitative selection of linguistic and speech material when studying a foreign language);

5) structural approach (mastering of a number of grammatical structures-samples which are arranged in a certain sequence, depending on the difficulty of their assimilation, taking into account their correct selection for subsequent communicative use);

6) competence approach (development of skills and abilities that allow to determine goals, then make decisions and act both in typical and non-standard situations);

7) sociocultural approach (development of understanding the culture as a broad interconnection of social phenomena which is the results and means of social activity and development);

8) communicative approach (formation of knowledge how to use the language depending on the purposes and functions of the utterance; how to properly use the language in accordance with the situation and participants; development of the ability to maintain a conversation despite the presence of limitations in one's knowledge of the language);

9) discursive approach (development of the ability to analyze the original texts identifying such discourse categories as audience, self-identification, time, space, intertextuality, inter-objectivity, inter-subjectivity, etc.);

10) consciously oriented approach (recognition of the similarity of the language being studied to the corresponding forms in the native language which means a positive transfer of phenomena from the native language to the foreign language).

Results

An individualized approach is most often used for organizing students' knowledge when teaching them a foreign language. The approach is aimed at ensuring that young people independently select, work with information, and use it in oral or written communication. To do this, students actively use such formats as 'the round table', debates, discussion, presentation, a five-minute speech, as well as the presentation of projects that can be presented, for example, in the form of a TV-presentation. These are non-standard activities designed to improve the forms of organization of knowledge when teaching a foreign language. The use of non-standard classes today is widely practiced as they contribute to a steady motivation for learning languages, and therefore, readiness for self-learning. In addition to the formats

mentioned above, we also include the following: classes in the form of competitions and games (competition, tournament, business game, role-playing game, quiz, etc.); classes that resemble public forms of communication (press conference, auction, rally, oral journal, etc.); studies based on the imitation of the activities of institutions and organizations (court, investigation, tribunal, patent office, academic council, etc.); classes that use traditional forms of out-of-class activities (a performance, a concert, a dramatization of a work of art, etc.); classes based on forms, genres and methods of work known in public practice (research, analysis of originals, comments, interviews, reporting, review, etc.). These and other forms of organization of knowledge when teaching a foreign language widely use the possibilities of the Internet which greatly extends the range of real communicative situations. It increases students' motivation, allows to apply acquired knowledge and skills to solve real-world communication problems. At the same time, the student can independently work on the language using certain types of exercises related to the formation of writing skills, listening, speaking, etc. For example, when teaching a letter, you can perform exercises aimed at the formation of lexical and grammatical knowledge and skills and carried out with the help of writing (written execution of lexical and grammatical training exercises for substitution, for completing sentences, putting up questions using specific lexical and grammatical material). There are also exercises that can serve as a means of developing other types of speech activity (writing out quotations from the text, a brief written interpretation of the content of the text, for example, in the form of a detailed answer to a question and others). Another example is a system of exercises for teaching listening which are preparatory exercises (for example, exercises for learning verbal hearing, exercises for learning probabilistic forecasting, exercises for the development of short-term and verbal-logical memory) and speech exercises (for example, exercises in the process of listening audio text).

Today methodological science shows an increasing interest in extra linguistic conditions for foreign-language communication, in the intellectual level of the learners, and their knowledge of the world at the general cultural level. This determines cultural and intellectual orientation of modern methods of teaching foreign languages, which selects as its object a linguistic personality that implements necessary lexical and grammatical structures that correspond to the norms of the speech activity of individuals from different linguistic communities. That is why teaching students a foreign language as a form of organization of their knowledge should be presented as a process for the transmission of linguistic and cultural experiences (the basis of this experience is the attitude of young people to themselves, to the world and the experience of creative activity in the course of mastering a foreign language and other cultures), which ideally should lead to an increase in their intellectual and general cultural level of knowledge. This position is the modern essence of linguistic education as a value, a result, a process and a system. In this regard, the following main tendencies of updating pedagogical system of higher education are determined: student's personality with highly developed intellectual potential becomes a system-forming element of the university; the strategic goal of education proclaims formation of real competence (social, intellectual, professional, ethno-cultural, moral, etc.) of the student as a person capable of self-determination, self-education, self-realization and self-actualization; modernization of the purposes, content and organization of the process of teaching students a foreign language as a form of organization of their knowledge is carried out on the basis of taking into account individual psychological characteristics of students, their needs and motives to learn and exercise the 'self'; the continuity of all levels of education is ensured with an orientation towards a holistic education throughout life; an adequate balance of the levels of vocational training and language culture of the student is determined by the management system of the learning process, taking into account modernization of the quality of education. This is due in particular to the fact

that recently in psychological and pedagogical studies much attention was paid to social intelligence which is understood as a complex of abilities underlying socio-cultural and communicative competence (competence in communication). A high level of social intelligence ensures a successful accomplishment of tasks in the adequate perception of a person by another person, establishing and maintaining contacts with other people, ensuring joint activities in a multicultural environment, occupying a high position in the society, etc. We also refer to the understanding of the intellect as an individual's ability to absorb already existing knowledge and skills in the society, as well as the ability to successfully apply them to solve problems of a different social orientation. At the same time, the intellectual potential itself is considered as an element of human potential existing along with the cultural potential, which is generally defined as the totality of the intellectual and sociocultural properties and qualities of an individual or group as a whole. As for increasing the intellectual and general cultural level of knowledge of students when studying a foreign language, it is carried out under the influence of internal and external factors that determine the individual's ability to be the subject of any changes in various spheres of public life. And this requires a high level and a corresponding quality of education for students, which, in fact, determines the opportunities for successful implementation of necessary activities, for example, participation in foreign communication.

Considering the improvement of the general cultural level of students' knowledge, we came to the conclusion that the process of teaching a foreign language is a process of personal development of a young person within the framework of developing it as a linguistic personality. Modern researchers consider the concept of the language personality as a constantly evolving category, in which both the subject and procedural aspects are reflected. The first aspect relates, as a rule, to the diverse knowledge involved in the process of teaching the subject 'Foreign Language'. The second aspect is, in fact, the skills and abilities to use acquired knowledge for the purpose of oral and / or written communication. Hence, if we are talking about the personal development abilities of the process of teaching a foreign language, then we mean the development of the personality as a whole, both its cultural (linguistic) aspects and intellectual (cognitive) aspects which are manifested primarily in the language. Therefore, the development of features of the language personality (linguistic abilities, skills, readiness for speech actions) that make students capable of being effective participants in intercultural communication is the strategic goal of teaching students a foreign language as a form of organizing knowledge. The final result of training is associated with the need not only to develop the learner's ability to use appropriate foreign-language 'techniques' but also to 'equip' the student with extensive extra-linguistic information necessary for adequate communication and mutual understanding at the intercultural level, and also develop such qualities that will allow to carry out direct and indirect communication with representatives of other cultures. This makes it possible to clearly distinguish, as priorities in the teaching of a foreign language, not simply the language system and the process of transferring the content of instruction to the trainees, but also the content aspects of education and, consequently, the interests and needs of students as subjects of the educational process. Hence, among modern methods such factors of learning are of importance: the sociocultural features of learning, motivation and mother tongue, development of the personality of the student in the process of confrontation with other cultures. It is important that selected content of instruction corresponds to experience and interests of students, and also that it is comparable to similar experience of their peers – representatives of other different cultures.

Discussion

Studying the problem of teaching students a foreign language as a form of organization of their knowledge revealed that teaching languages stimulates the processes of comprehending the socio-cultural portrait of the country of the studied language on the basis of the penetration of representatives of another linguistic society into the language culture. At the same time, the study of a foreign language promotes: formation of the ability to independently search for knowledge; active use of algorithms of mental activity; development of attention and memory; development of imagination and intuition; development of reflection (the ability to evaluate one's actions in an unpredictable language situation); and most importantly – an increasing desire to constantly learn with the goal of self-development and self-realization in any field of activity. This is connected with the most important goal of teaching a foreign language – development of a communicative competence which includes such necessary components as: linguistic knowledge and language skills for recognition and generation of information; communicative skills in speaking, listening, reading and writing; cultural knowledge to ensure the socio-cultural background of communication, without which the formation of communicative competence is impossible.

Thus, modern education is directly related to the competitiveness of the graduate, which now depends on his ability to learn, namely, the ability to independently acquire knowledge and work with information. Obviously, the problem of students' readiness for self-education throughout life depends on the development of the skills of independent learning activity in institutions of higher education. This means the student fulfills own tasks, independently of others, which contributes to the development of a high level of the student's independence and the manifestation of own abilities. These abilities, in particular, are manifested as follows: language abilities (student's readiness for various actions with systems of linguistic symbols); linguistic abilities (they constitute an integral part of a person's cognitive ability – auditory differential sensitivity, memory, verbal-logical thinking); speaking abilities (the ability to operate in the process of communication by means of systems other than the native language system); analytical linguistic ability (represented by verbal intellect and ability to the linguistic reflection).

However, when teaching students a foreign language as a form of knowledge organization, it is necessary to take into account the fact that this represents a specific set of certain psychological properties. Successful learning of a foreign language requires the following: fast, lasting and complete memorization of foreign verbal material; distribution of attention between the language form and content; transfer of learned linguistic units and speech actions to changing conditions; successful management by the student himself of the process of mastering a foreign language. It is necessary not only to obtain students' profound knowledge of a foreign language for the effectiveness of the educational process but also to use this knowledge productively, i.e. it is assumed that students should know where and how they can use the knowledge they have gained.

Conclusion

The modern educational ideology with its clearly expressed personally oriented focus of training and an active character dictates the need to formulate the basic requirements for the methodological foundations of teaching students a foreign language as a form of organizing knowledge. It is necessary that teaching students a foreign language gives an opportunity for all the stakeholders of the educational process to focus on the content of their activities and objectively assess the results achieved. The objectives of teaching a foreign language at each stage of education in university should take into account the principle of interrelation between the goals of teaching a foreign language with general educational

purposes. The success of teaching students a foreign language depends fully on the degree to which the educational model of the university being created is close to reality and real practice in the chosen field. Training students in a foreign language is designed to satisfy the individual educational trajectory of each student and their further self-education (that is, there should not be strict regulation of specific methods and methods of teaching). Universal realization in high school education should receive a sociocultural aspect of the goal, a variety of learned functional types of the language, attitudes associated with the increase of the philological culture of students with the expansion of their general cultural outlook, an increase of the intellectual potential of students with the possible use of a foreign language in their future professional activities. Thus, orientation toward an individual strategy for the development of a student's personality naturally leads to the change in the correlation of normative requirements to the quality of education and the requirements for self-determination, self-education, independence and self-realization in educational and professional activities. Hence, at the present stage of the development of the system of language education, the following should become a priority: training of qualified specialists capable and ready to carry out productive activities in a multicultural environment; ensuring the formation of a modern system of continuous language education and its continuity; improving the quality of foreign language education, taking into account national and international requirements; activation of innovative processes in language education, taking into account the successful organization of cognitive activity of students; ensuring the possibility of studying several foreign languages; integration of educational, scientific and practical activities of students.

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